

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Enhancing CIGS Solar Cell Performance with Erbium-Doped TiO₂ Nanomaterial: Simulation Study

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Abstract

Objectives: To find a proper rare earth-doped metal-oxide-based buffer layer for CIGS solar cells with improved performance that has less harmfulness than cadmium. **Methods:** This study concentrated on the synthesis of pure and Er-doped TiO₂ nanomaterials via microwave-assisted hydrothermal method and its characterization results. Additionally, to analyze the performance of TiO₂ and Er-doped TiO₂ as a buffer layer in a CIGS solar cell, numerical simulations were performed using the SCAPS-1D (Solar cell capacitance simulator) software. **Findings:** The positive outcomes came from the characterization results, which revealed that the synthesized nanomaterials have an anatase phase, microscopic crystallite size, and flower-like shape. The band gap effectively decreases from 3.45 eV for pure TiO₂ to 2.75 eV for Er-doped TiO₂, which effectively increases the absorption in the visible portion of the solar spectrum. The refractive indices of pure and Er-doped TiO₂ were calculated as 2.37 and 2.50 respectively from their corresponding band gaps. The results from the simulations showed that using a single buffer layer of Er-doped TiO₂ uplifted the performance of the CIGS solar cell, resulting in higher open circuit voltage, increased short-circuit current density with overall efficiency, $\eta = 25.31\%$ compared to pure TiO₂ and CdS-based dual buffer layers. **Novelty:** For the first time, the Er-TiO₂ nanomaterial was studied as buffer layer material. The numerical simulation and characterization findings justify the adoption of Er-TiO₂ as a buffer layer in CIGS solar cells.

Keywords: Hydrothermal method; Erbium; Buffer layer; CIGS; SCAPS

1 Introduction

The development of silicon (Si) solar cells opened the door for harnessing solar energy because they provide a sustainable and eco-friendly technique to produce electricity. Due to their high photovoltaic performance, cheap material cost, and versatility, CIGS

(copper indium gallium selenide) solar cells are a category of thin-film photovoltaic technology that has drawn considerable interest as a possible replacement for normal silicon-based solar cells.⁽¹⁾ The window layer, buffer layer, and absorber layer are the three main layers that makeup CIGS solar cells. Of these aforementioned layers, the researchers are more focused on the buffer layer. Since the buffer layer is crucial in helping the absorber layer by promoting the construction of the bridge that links the window layer and the absorber layer. Additionally, by adjusting the band alignment between the window and the absorber layer, the buffer layer can improve the charge carrier collection and lessen recombination-related losses.⁽²⁾ Normally, Cadmium sulfide (CdS) has been extensively used as a buffer layer for CIGS due to its favorable band alignment with the absorber layer.⁽³⁾ It is difficult to use CdS in real-world solar cell applications because of its harmful nature, which limits its use as a buffer layer in CIGS solar cells.⁽³⁾

Research investigations are concentrated on finding a better replacement for CdS. Several alternatives have been used to date like ZnO, ZnSe, ZnS, SiC, In₂S₃, ZrS_xSe_{2-x}, and SnO₂.^(4,5) The remarkable efficiency of 23.25% was noted by the researchers using Zn[O,S,OH]_x/Zn_{0.8}Mg_{0.2}O as a dual buffer layer in the fabricated CIGSSe solar cell.⁽⁶⁾ For this work, a less toxic metal oxide semiconductor material (namely titanium dioxide) was chosen as the buffer layer. TiO₂ is an appealing material for this application due to its wide band gap, flexible optical and electrical characteristics, chemical and thermal stability, and inexpensive, making it a promising option for large-scale solar cell production.⁽⁷⁾ The simulation study of TiO₂ as a buffer layer in CIGS solar cells using AFORS-HET software gives an efficiency of 16.03%.⁽⁸⁾ Reports suggest that adding rare-earth elements to TiO₂ can refine the band gap, increase carrier lifetime, and improve charge transport.⁽⁷⁾ In this study, Erbium (Er), one of the rare earth materials, was used as a dopant, hoping to potentially enrich the performance of the TiO₂ buffer layer. The fabrication of dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) with Er-doped TiO₂ showed an efficiency of 4.62%, whereas DSSC with pure TiO₂ shows only 2.88%.⁽⁹⁾ The TiO₂ and Er-doped TiO₂ nanomaterials were prepared via a single-step microwave-assisted hydrothermal process, offering advantages such as high yield, uniform size distribution, reduced reaction time, cost-effectiveness, and eco-friendliness.⁽¹⁰⁾

The present work covers the preparation of TiO₂ and Er-TiO₂ nanomaterials and the interpretation of characterization results obtained from powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) analysis, high-resolution transmission electron microscopic (HR-TEM) analysis, and UV-visible spectroscopic analysis. Furthermore, the article discusses the numerical simulation of CIGS solar cells with TiO₂ and Er-TiO₂ as buffer layers using SCAPS-1D software.

2 Methodology

The precise steps involved in the preparation of the nanomaterials are schematized in Figure 1.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 PXRD analysis

The 2θ and intensity values were recorded using a Rigaku Ultima IV X-Ray Diffractometer with a 1.5406 Å wavelength of CuK α radiation. The lattice parameters, the unit cell volume, (h k l) planes indexing, bravais lattice, and space group were identified using General Structure Analysis Software-II (GSAS-II).⁽¹¹⁾ The peaks of the pure and 1 mol% Er-doped TiO₂ nanomaterials belong to the anatase phase, which was known from the GSAS-II results, and it was also confirmed by correlating the peaks with JCPDS file no. 21-1272, which was schematized in Figure 2. Studies suggest that the efficient electron mobility of the anatase phase TiO₂ makes it a promising option to use in solar cells.⁽¹²⁾

The average crystallite size of the nanomaterials was calculated using the Debye-Scherrer relation.⁽⁹⁾ The high-intensity peak of 1 mol% Er-doped TiO₂ was wider compared to the peak of pure TiO₂, leading to a decrease in crystallite size in Er-doped TiO₂ nanomaterials.⁽¹³⁾ Venkatachalam et al. also reported the crystallite size reduction due to the wider peaks.⁽⁹⁾ In addition, the parameters detailed in Table 1 show that the decrease in lattice parameters and the unit cell volume of the Er-doped TiO₂ may be significant due to the big ionic radius of the erbium ion (0.89 Å) whereas the ionic radius of titanium is 0.605 Å.⁽¹⁴⁾ According to Table 1, the volume of the unit cell for Er-doped TiO₂ shrank along with the drop of the average crystallite size, possibly signifying that the entry of Er³⁺ ions led the surface area to rise by shrinking the unit cell, which is highly useful in photocatalytic behavior.⁽¹⁵⁾ The capacity of the Er-TiO₂ nanomaterial to absorb light naturally increases with an increase in surface area.

Fig 1. Synthesis procedure of pure and Er-doped TiO₂ nanomaterials

Fig 2. PXRD pattern of pure and Er-doped TiO₂ nanomaterials

Table 1. Parameters calculated using GSAS-II software

Nanomaterial	a=b (Å)	c (Å)	Volume of the unit cell (Å ³)	Structure	Space group	Average crystallite size, $D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta}$ [nm]
TiO ₂	3.82	9.50	138.27	tetragonal body-centered	<i>I4₁/amd</i>	5.41 ⁽³⁾
1 mol% Er-doped TiO ₂	3.82	9.45	137.68	tetragonal body-centered	<i>I4₁/amd</i>	5.19 ⁽³⁾

3.2 HR-TEM analysis

The HR-TEM analysis was conducted using a JOEL TEM 2100 High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscope. The TEM pictures of pure TiO_2 and 1 mol% Er-doped TiO_2 revealed a flower-like nanoparticle structure, as shown in Figure 3 [a] and [b]. The polycrystalline nature of the nanomaterials was visible through the rings observed in the Selected Area Electron Diffraction (SAED) pattern, which was seen in Figure 3 [c] and [d]. The d-spacing values were identified using ImageJ software.⁽¹⁶⁾ The lattice fringe width (d-spacing) for the (101) plane was predicted as 3.65 Å and 3.571 Å, as portrayed in Figure 3 [e] and [f]. The (h k l) planes and d-spacing values discovered using ImageJ software were also validated by the GSAS-II results. Khurshid Ahmad et al. exposed that the nanomaterial with a flower-like structure has a large surface area when compared with other structures,⁽¹⁷⁾ and hence, using a flower-structured material in solar cells may increase the cell's efficiency.

Fig 3. Comparison of TEM pictures, SAED pattern and lattice images of TiO_2 and Er- TiO_2

3.3 UV — visible spectroscopic analysis

The absorption characteristics of TiO_2 and Er- TiO_2 nanomaterials were examined using the JASCO UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The absorption spectra of TiO_2 nanomaterials exhibited peaks at 235 nm and 280 nm in the UV area, as revealed in Figure 4 [a]. In contrast, the absorption of 1 mol% Er-doped TiO_2 nanomaterials decreased in the UV region but increased in the visible region. The indirect band gap (E_g) of pure TiO_2 and 1 mol% Er-doped TiO_2 was determined to be 3.45 eV and 2.75 eV, respectively, using the Tauc plot (Figure 4 [b]). This kind of decrement in band gap value was also reported by Mutalib et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ The considerable reduction in band gap may have been produced by oxygen vacancies brought on by the doping of Er^{3+} ions.⁽¹⁹⁾

Fig 4. Images of [a] absorbance graph and [b] Tauc's plot

A CIGS solar cell's efficiency is closely correlated with the buffer layer's refractive index. Limiting reflection losses at the interface between the adjacent layers also depends on the buffer layer and the CIGS absorber layer's refractive index matching.⁽²⁰⁾ The increased reflection losses can be caused by an imbalance in the refractive indices, which decreases solar cell efficiency. The CIGS absorber layer's refractive index commonly falls between 2.54 and 3.05.⁽²¹⁾ The refractive index (n) from the energy gap was calculated using Equation (1) presented by Ravindra et al.,⁽²²⁾

$$E_g n^4 = 108 \tag{1}$$

The refractive index was calculated as 2.37 and 2.50 for TiO₂ and 1 mol% Er-doped TiO₂ respectively. These results indicate that due to the matching of the refractive index of Er-TiO₂ material with the absorbance layer, CIGS solar cells with an Er-doped TiO₂ buffer layer may have greater efficiency than CIGS solar cells based solely on TiO₂.

3.4 Modelling and simulation in SCAPS-1D

Numerical simulation has emerged as a cost-effective and time-efficient tool for studying solar cells and optimizing their designs. The SCAPS-1D is widely accepted for its accuracy and versatility in simulating solar cells.⁽⁴⁾ The behavior of the cell in one direction typically perpendicular to the substrate can easily be studied in SCAPS-1D. The Equations (2), (3) and (4) which respectively describe Poisson's equation and continuity equations, both explain how charges move through the device.⁽⁵⁾

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} = -\frac{q}{\epsilon} \left[p - n + N_D^+ - N_A^- + \frac{\rho_{def}}{q} \right] \tag{2}$$

$$-\frac{\partial J_n}{\partial x} - R_n + G[x] = \frac{\partial n}{\partial t} \tag{3}$$

$$-\frac{\partial J_p}{\partial x} - R_p + G[x] = \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \tag{4}$$

Where ϕ - electrostatic potential [V], ϵ - dielectric constant of the material, q - electric charge [C], p - hole concentration [m^{-3}], n - electron concentration [m^{-3}], N_D^+ - donor concentration [cm^{-3}], N_A^- - acceptor concentration [cm^{-3}], ρ_{def} - defect charge density [cm^{-3}], J_n - electron current density [A/m^2], J_p - hole current density [A/m^2], R_n - electron recombination rate [cm^{-3}] and R_p - hole recombination rate [cm^{-3}].

The electron-hole pair generated during the simulation was given as the generation (G[x]) as in the Equation (5).

$$G(x) = \int_{\lambda_{min}}^{\lambda_{max}} \alpha(\lambda, x) \cdot N_{photon}(\lambda, x) d\lambda \tag{5}$$

Where λ_{min} - minimum wavelength [m] and λ_{max} - maximum wavelength [m], α - absorption coefficient [1/m], and N_{photon} - spectrum of the incident photon.

3.4.1 Device configuration and simulation of the proposed CIGS solar cell

Fig 5. SCAPS simulated CIGS solar cell device structure

The simulated CIGS solar cell has the succeeding structure: front contact/ZnO:Al/i-ZnO/buffer layer/CIGS/back contact as shown in Figure 5. The in-built solar spectrum file AM1.5G of the SCAPS 1-D was used in the simulation. Specifically, the cell's temperature was fixed at 300 K. The work done by Mebelson et al. served as the basis for the ZnO:Al, CdS, and CIGS layer specifications.⁽¹⁾ The layer parameters of i-ZnO used here were loaded from SCAPS. Except for the bandgap and dielectric permittivity, the other parameters of TiO₂ and Er-TiO₂ were all set to default, which are listed in Table 2. A 60 nm thick buffer layer was utilized in this simulation. The simulation employed five distinct buffer layer configurations, including single buffer layers of TiO₂ and Er-TiO₂, and dual buffer layers consisting of TiO₂/CdS, Er-TiO₂/CdS, and TiO₂/Er-TiO₂.

Table 2. List of parameters used in the simulation

Parameters	ZnO:Al	i-ZnO	CdS	TiO ₂	Er-TiO ₂	CIGS
Thickness [nm]	200	55	variable	variable	variable	2000
Bandgap [eV]	3.3	3.400	2.400	3.45	2.75	1.2
Electron affinity [eV]	4.4	4.000	4.200	3.9	3.9	3.89
Dielectric permittivity [relative]	10	9.000	10.000	17.80	13.78	13.6
CB effective density of states [1/cm ³]	2.2E+18	2.2E+18	2.2E+18	1.0E+19	1.0E+19	2.2E+18
VB effective density of states [1/cm ³]	1.8E+19	1.8E+19	1.8E+19	1.0E+19	1.0E+19	1.8E+19
Electron thermal velocity [cm/s]	1.0E+7	1.0E+7	1.0E+7	1.0E+7	1.0E+7	1.0E+7
Hole thermal velocity [cm/s]	1.0E+7	1.0E+7	1.0E+7	1.0E+7	1.0E+7	1.0E+7
Electron mobility [cm ² /Vs]	10.0E+1	5.000E+1	5.000E+0	2.0E+1	2.0E+1	2.5E+1
Hole mobility [cm ² /Vs]	2.5E+1	5.000E+0	5.000E+0	1.0E+1	1.0E+1	1.0E+1
Shallow uniform donor density ND [1/cm ³]	5.000E+17	5.000E+17	1.000E+18	1.0E+16	1.0E+16	-
Shallow uniform acceptor density NA [1/cm ³]	-	-	-	-	-	5.000E+17

3.4.2 Analysis of current density-voltage curve

The J-V graph can expose significant parameters such as the fill factor (FF), short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), and open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}). These variables offer insightful data regarding the functionality and effectiveness of the solar cell. The FF and efficiency (η) were calculated by using the Equations (6) and (7).⁽²³⁾

$$FF = \frac{V_{max} \times I_{max}}{V_{oc} \times I_{sc}} \quad (6)$$

$$\eta = \frac{V_{oc} \times I_{sc} \times FF}{Intensity\ of\ light} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

The J-V curve for the single-layer Er-TiO₂ solar cell shown in Figure 6 [a] performs particularly well among the simulated CIGS solar cells. The inset graph in Figure 6 [a] shows an enlarged view of the variation of current density in different buffer layers. The V_{oc} values for the various buffer layers are relatively similar, differing from 0.7312 V to 0.7319 V. The J_{sc} values for the different buffer layers are also quite alike, ranging from 40.16 mA/cm² to 41.02 mA/cm². All five chosen buffer layers exhibited nearly identical maximum voltage and current output when irradiated with the AM1.5G spectrum. However, there was noticeable variability in the FF and η values across the different buffer layers. The Er-TiO₂ and TiO₂/Er-TiO₂ buffer layers have the highest FF value of 84.30 %, while the TiO₂/CdS buffer layer has the lowest FF value of 84.05 %.

Findings in Table 3 demonstrate that the efficiency of CIGS solar cells with TiO₂-based buffer layers (TiO₂, Er-TiO₂, and TiO₂/Er-TiO₂) are on par with or superior to those with CdS-based buffer layers (TiO₂/CdS and Er-TiO₂/CdS). Particularly, compared to the CdS-based buffer layers, the TiO₂-based buffer layers exhibit a marginally greater efficiency. The efficiencies of the TiO₂/CdS and Er-TiO₂/CdS buffer layers are 24.86% and 25.15%, respectively, while those of the TiO₂, Er-TiO₂, and TiO₂/Er-TiO₂ buffer layers are 24.75%, 25.31%, and 25.04%. The simulation work done by Leila Ghalmi et al. reported an efficiency of 23.12% for CIGS solar cells with a ZnS-buffer layer.⁽²⁴⁾ Thus, the current investigation shows that TiO₂-based buffer layers for CIGS solar cells are an effective substitute for CdS-based buffer layers since they can deliver comparable or higher performance.

Table 3. Output parameters obtained from the simulation

Buffer layer materials	V_{oc} [V]	J_{sc} [mA/cm ²]	FF [%]	η [%]
TiO ₂	0.7312	40.16	84.27	24.75
Er-TiO ₂	0.7319	41.02	84.30	25.31
TiO ₂ /CdS	0.7313	40.44	84.05	24.86
Er-TiO ₂ /CdS	0.7316	40.89	84.07	25.15
TiO ₂ /Er-TiO ₂	0.7316	40.59	84.30	25.04

3.4.3 Analysis of quantum efficiency (QE) curve

The Quantum efficiency of a solar cell is proportional to the number of charge carriers produced in the external circuit by incident photons of a particular wavelength. The quantum efficiency graph of the CIGS solar cells with Er-TiO₂, TiO₂/CdS, Er-TiO₂/CdS, and TiO₂/Er-TiO₂ as the buffer layers were almost looking similar, which was visible in Figure 6 [c] and [d]. On the other hand, the CIGS solar cell's quantum efficiency, which is based on TiO₂ begins at a wavelength of 700 nm as shown in Figure 6 [b].

Fig 6. J-V curve and QE curve of the simulated CIGS solar cell

4 Conclusion

Using a single stage of microwave assistance, hydrothermal preparation was used to synthesize anatase TiO₂ and Er-doped TiO₂ nanomaterials. After the addition of Er³⁺ ions to TiO₂, favorable results were obtained, like a small crystallite size and a reduction of the band gap. For the very first time, the CIGS solar cells with TiO₂, Er-TiO₂, TiO₂/CdS, Er-TiO₂/CdS, and TiO₂/Er-TiO₂ as buffer layers were simulated and their J-V characteristic curves were analyzed. TiO₂ shows an efficiency of 24.75%, but its quantum efficiency is poor. Er-doped TiO₂ with 25.31% efficiency (percentage of increase is 2.26%) shows a good spectral response as a CdS-based dual buffer layer. In addition, there is no significant difference between the efficiencies of the Er-TiO₂-based and CdS-based CIGS solar cells. Besides, TiO₂-based nanomaterials are less toxic and more environmentally

friendly than CdS, which is an additional advantage for their use in solar cell applications. These results recommend that erbium-doped TiO₂ can be a hopeful candidate to serve as a buffer layer in CIGS solar cells.

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